

LETTER • OPEN ACCESS

Climate change drives coastal oligotrophication in a high-Arctic fjord via terrestrial greening and freshwater input

To cite this article: Dorte H Sogaard *et al* 2025 *Environ. Res. Commun.* 7 061012

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [The making of rights of nature: nine patterns in a decade of empirical research on social-ecological drivers and actors](#)
Ilkhom Soliev, Frauke Pirscher and Marie Schreiber
- [Charting plastic shores: environmental NGOs bridging historical data gaps for coastal litter management in Cyprus](#)
Ioannis Savva, Maria Kola, Natasa Ioannou et al.
- [Carbon footprints of different household types: the sharing benefit illusion](#)
Jukka Heinonen and Sarah Olson

www.hidenanalytical.com
info@hiden.co.uk

HIDEN ANALYTICAL

Instruments for Advanced Science

Mass spectrometers for vacuum, gas, plasma and surface science

Dissolved Species Analysis

Hiden offers MIMS capabilities in the form of a benchtop HPR-40 DSA system for laboratory-based research and the portable case mounted pQA for applications that favour in-situ measurements in the field. Both are supplied with a choice of membrane material and user-changeable sample inlets.

Gas Analysis

The QGA and HPR-20 series gas analysers are versatile tools designed for a broad spectrum of environmental applications, including pollution monitoring, biogas analysis, and sustainable energy research.

Environmental Research Communications

LETTER

Climate change drives coastal oligotrophication in a high-Arctic fjord via terrestrial greening and freshwater input

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED

28 January 2025

REVISED

23 May 2025

ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION

3 June 2025

PUBLISHED

30 June 2025

Original content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

Dorte H Søgaard^{1,2,3}

¹ Greenland Climate Research Centre, Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Kivioq 2, PO Box 570, 3900 Nuuk, Greenland

² Arctic Research Centre, Department of Biology, Aarhus University, Ole Worms Allé 1, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

³ Department of Biology, Aarhus University, CIFAR Research Centre, Ole Worms Allé 1, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

⁴ Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

⁵ Department of Environment and Minerals, Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Kivioq 2, PO Box 570, 3900 Nuuk, Greenland

⁶ Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, C.F. Møllers Alle, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

⁷ Centre for Earth Observation Science, CHR Faculty of Environment Earth and Resources, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada

⁸ Water, Energy and Environmental Engineering Research Unit, Faculty of Technology, University of Oulu, Finland

⁹ Oulanka Research Station, University of Oulu, 93900 Kuusamo, Finland

¹⁰ Department of Biological Sciences, University of Notre Dame, Notre Dame, Indiana, 46656, United States of America

E-mail: doso@natur.gl

Keywords: nutrient input, nitrate concentrations, phytoplankton biomass, primary production

Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Nutrient inputs from upwelling, ocean currents, advection, and terrestrial sources play a crucial role in driving primary production in Arctic fjords and coastal areas. This study analyzes more than two decades of field measurements across a terrestrial-river-coastal continuum in Arctic Greenland, showing how shifts in coastal inflows, glacial meltwater, and terrestrial inputs control changes in nutrient dynamics in the fjord. Our data indicate oligotrophication, with nitrate concentrations decreasing by ~49% and phytoplankton biomass by ~60% over the study period. These changes are associated with a ~12% increase in catchment vegetation greening, which likely reduced terrestrial nitrate input to the fjord by ~65%. Nutrient dynamics in the fjord were also influenced by inflows of fresher coastal waters, providing nitrate-poor, silicate-rich waters. Silicate concentrations in the fjord have risen by ~115% over the past two decades, suggesting increased input from all these sources. Whether these patterns are unique to this fjord or representative of broader Arctic trends remains uncertain and our study highlights the need to further explore the cross-boundary ecological impacts of climate change on Arctic marine and coastal ecosystems.

1. Introduction

As the effects of climate change continue to intensify, the Arctic is warming three to four times faster than the rest of the world [1, 2], causing profound regional changes. In addition to the general Arctic warming, there are also substantial local environmental and ecological effects, such as an unprecedented increase in the annual volume of meltwater and solid ice discharge from receding glaciers, permafrost thaw, and altered extent and duration of sea ice and snow cover [3, 4]. These changes may have profound impacts on Arctic terrestrial and freshwater systems, as well as the fjords and coastal areas [5–7], by altering biogeochemical cycles, primary production [8, 9], and overall ecosystem functioning [10–12].

Rapid and pronounced warming is also driving a general increase in high-Arctic terrestrial productivity [13], although with large spatiotemporal variability of net primary productivity and changes in greening and browning patterns [2, 13, 14]. In Greenland there has been a general increase in terrestrial greening [13], likely due to climate-induced changes and local redistribution of terrestrial nutrient pools that enhance plant productivity [14] driven by lateral transport and permafrost thawing [15]. This increased terrestrial greening may result in reduced terrestrial nutrient inputs from land to rivers, and further to fjords and coastal waters [16, 17].

As with terrestrial greening, primary production in high Arctic coastal waters, and across the Arctic Ocean, has also increased over the past two decades [9]. These increases can be explained by a longer ice-free period, an extended pelagic growth season [18–20], as well as increased inorganic nitrogen (N) supplied by rivers and coastal erosion [21, 22]. Considerable effort has recently been devoted to studying changes in nutrient distributions and productivity in Greenland fjords [23–28]. However, the interactions between physical drivers (e.g., oceanic inflows and melting glaciers) and the transport of dissolved nutrients from land, river outflows, and from the adjacent oceans remain poorly understood. Similar complexity is related to the coastal light climate, where loss of sea ice combined with increased turbidity from terrestrial runoff resulting in spatiotemporal changes in annual light availability that are not fully resolved [29].

In this study, we propose that recent shifts in nutrient availability across the Arctic may lead to localized declines in pelagic primary production, which contrasts with the overall increase in primary production recently observed in the Arctic Ocean [8]. This assertion is based on two significant climate-related changes. First, inflows of coastal waters from the East Greenland Current (EGC) have been freshening [30, 31]. Although sources of freshwater to the EGC are difficult to distinguish, recent research suggests that river input from East Siberia is the major contributor, along with a smaller local contribution from the Greenland Ice Sheet [32, 33]. Both of these sources carry silicate-rich [34–36] but nitrate-poor water [8, 20, 37], and the increased freshwater enhances stratification, inhibiting the upwelling of nutrients that are critical for primary production in the photic zone [25, 35]. The Laptev Sea, off the northern coast of Siberia, receives substantial freshwater discharge from major rivers such as the Lena River, and is connected to the EGC through the Transpolar drift. This influx, combined with a general increase in Arctic phytoplankton production due to longer open-water periods, delivers nitrate-poor waters to the EGC [8, 21, 37].

Furthermore, increased greening of the terrestrial landscape may reduce nitrate runoff from land to sea, due to increased assimilation by vegetation [16]. Tundra vegetation is generally nitrogen-limited [38, 39], suggesting that newly available nitrate is likely to be assimilated immediately by terrestrial vegetation.

Here we document how High Arctic fjord nutrient dynamics in Young Sound in Northeast Greenland are closely linked to terrestrial greening and inflow of fresher coastal waters, using two decades of ecosystem wide field data from across the terrestrial–river–coastal system. To our knowledge, this study provides the first observational, data-driven temporal analysis of cross-ecosystem linkages from land to coast in the High Arctic. By using a unique, dataset from NE Greenland spanning two decades, we investigate how changes in lowland vegetation greening, along with inflows of fresher coastal waters and the melting of the Greenland Ice Sheet, have led to a decline in nitrate concentrations and phytoplankton biomass in the fjord. More specifically, we demonstrate that nitrate concentrations have declined in river and fjord waters over the past two decades, while greening of the lowland tundra habitat has increased. These results highlight the crucial role of long-term monitoring across interconnected terrestrial, river and coastal ecosystems in understanding the full scope of climate-driven changes in Arctic ecosystems.

2. Materials and methods

To ensure a consistent and ecologically relevant cross-ecosystem comparison, only August data from fjord, riverine, and terrestrial environments are included.

2.1. Pelagic sampling in the fjord

All data from the fjord are collected as part of the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) Program [40–44]. The ‘Standard Station’ (74°18′N, 20°18′W) lies in the outer part of fjord and is the location for the ongoing collection of time series data on marine processes [44], this station was selected to represent the conditions in Young Sound. Hydrographic profiles, nutrient and Chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) data were obtained during peak freshwater discharge in August from 2003 to 2023 (three sampling days per year) from the ‘Standard Station’. Hydrographic profiles were obtained using a CTD profiler (SeaBird 19+ & RBR Maestro) [44]. Water samples were collected using a Niskin water sampler at 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30 and 50 meter depths. They were analyzed for [NO₃ + NO₂] (hereafter referred to as nitrate, as >90% of [NO₃ + NO₂] is in the form of nitrate) on a NO_x analyzer (Model 42V, Thermo Environmental Instruments) after reduction to NO in hot vanadium chloride.

Silicate ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$) and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) were determined by standard colorimetric methods and analyzed automatically on a robotic sample processor coupled to a spectrophotometer (Gilson 222 XL & Shimadzu 1600 PC) [26]. Detection limits for nitrate, phosphate and silicate were 0.15, 0.20 and 0.25 μM , respectively [27]. Chl *a* were determined using ethanol extraction and fluorometric analysis (Turner Designs Trilogy) [45].

2.2. Terrestrial sampling

The *in situ* spectral maximum normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI_{max}) data [46] was sampled as part of the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) Program. The NDVI was measured in 23 permanent vegetation plots (each with four replicates), covering all major vegetation types (i.e., dry and moist heaths and wet meadows) in the lowland of the Zackenberg Valley [47]. These plots are thus considered representative of the vegetated parts of the lowland catchment area. The lowland NDVI plots were measured on a near-weekly basis from snowmelt to late August between 1999 and 2023 using one of three methods: Handheld RVI Skye sensor (1999–2007), handheld CropCircle (2007–2019), and a drone-based Sequoia camera (2019–2023). To arrive at a landscape-level description of plant greenness, we first calculated the NDVI_{max} for each of the six dominant vegetation types within each of the 23 plots and then calculated the annual average across these NDVI_{max} values across the plots. In all plots, the NDVI_{max} typically is found in early August.

2.3. River sampling

Nitrate concentrations in Zackenberg river have been obtained from river water chemistry dataset [48]. All river samples were collected at a site 800 m from the outlet of the Zackenberg River ($74^\circ 28' \text{N}$, $20^\circ 34' \text{W}$) to the Young Sound Fjord. For the analysis, we only used August samples to compare with the marine samples: in different years the number of August samples varied from 4 (in 2013) to 40 (in 2021). Water samples were stored at $+6^\circ\text{C}$, before analysis. 2006–2023 was done on Fiastar 5000 Flow Analyzer. We calculated annual average values \pm Standard Deviation (SD) for nitrate for all years between 2006 and 2023. The total catchment area is 3,016 km^2 and the contribution of the total river discharge (all rivers) to the Young Sound fjord system was modelled as 0.9 to 1.4 km^3 annually [49, 50].

2.4. Data treatment and analysis

For all fjord data, we calculated the average values across seven depth levels (1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, and 50 meters). Stratification of the water column was calculated applying the φ concept as based on the difference in potential energy between a fully mixed and a stratified water column [51]. For NDVI we calculated the overall NDVI_{max} as the highest annual NDVI value observed within each of the six dominant vegetation types monitored (dry and moist heaths, snowbeds and fens) during the 1999–2023 period. We then calculated the average NDVI_{max} values \pm SD per year. To identify potential freshwater sources, we compared our nitrate to phosphate ratios with findings from previous studies [32, 38, 52]. We analyzed the relationships between silicate and salinity, as well as nitrate and salinity, to assess whether nutrient dynamics evolved in parallel with the ongoing freshening in the study area. To evaluate temporal changes in both fjord, river and terrestrial conditions, we performed simple linear regressions, including an analysis of the temporal trends in NDVI_{max} across different vegetation types. To test the robustness of our findings, we also conducted weighted linear regressions in which years with greater data availability and lower uncertainty were given more weight, while years with higher variability were down weighted. These supplementary analyses confirmed the overall trends and are provided in the Supplementary Material (table S1). We estimated the vertical nitrate flux in the water column as $\text{NF} = -K_z (\Delta\text{N}) / (\Delta Z)$ with a vertical eddy diffusivity of mass as $K_z = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ [53, 54].

3. Results

Our analysis reveals a long-term decline in August nutrient availability and phytoplankton biomass (Chlorophyll *a*) in the surface water in Young Sound (figures 1(a) and (d)). Between 2003 and 2023, average nitrate concentrations within the upper 50 meters decreased from $1.25 \pm 0.13 \mu\text{M}$ to $0.63 \pm 0.61 \mu\text{M}$ (figure 1(a)); Chl *a* concentration declined from $0.88 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{g Chl } a \text{ L}^{-1}$ in 2004 to $0.35 \pm 0.31 \mu\text{g Chl } a \text{ L}^{-1}$ in 2023 (figure 1(d)). In the same period, silicate concentrations rose by $\sim 115\%$, increasing from 1.80 ± 0.35 to $3.80 \pm 0.97 \mu\text{M}$ (figure 1(c)), whereas phosphate concentrations showed no significant trends, fluctuating between $0.39 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{M}$ to $0.55 \pm 0.11 \mu\text{M}$ (figure 1(b)). Overall, there was a $\sim 49\%$ reduction in surface nitrate concentration and a $\sim 60\%$ reduction in surface phytoplankton biomass during summer.

Surface water salinity in the upper 50 meters decreased by $\sim 2.5\%$ from 30.70 ± 0.26 to 29.30 ± 3.10 (figure 1(e)). This decrease in salinity coincided with a $\sim 75\%$ increase in stratification strength (φ) (figure 1(f)). Additionally, the estimated nitrate flux from bottom waters to the 0–50 m layer decreased by $0.23 \text{ mmol N m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, though this decrease was not statistically significant ($p > 0.1$).

Across the study period, a significant decrease in riverine nitrate concentration (figure 2(a)) and a significant increase in terrestrial vegetation greening were observed (figure 2(b)). Between 2006 and 2023, riverine nitrate concentrations declined by $\sim 65\%$, from 1.91 ± 0.20 to $0.75 \pm 0.58 \mu\text{M}$ (figure 2(a)). Concurrently, NDVI_{max} increased by $\sim 12\%$, from 0.59 ± 0.1 in 1999 to 0.66 ± 0.1 in 2023, indicating a clear greening trend in the lowland tundra (figure 2(b)).

To trace potential freshwater sources, we compared nitrate to phosphate (N:P) ratios from the surface waters in Young Sound with published records (figure 3(a)). Our N:P ratios are slightly comparable to those from the Laptev Sea [38] and the Northeast Greenland Shelf [32], differing from those of Atlantic and Pacific waters [52]. Assuming that nutrient uptake followed the standard Redfield-Brezekinski ratio of 106C:16N:15Si:1P, then nitrate (N:P ratio between 0.20 to 8.50), appeared to have limited algal production (figure 3(a)).

The relationship between silicate and salinity (figures 3(b), (c)) and nitrate and salinity (figures 3(d), (e)) further reinforces the pattern between nutrient dynamics and ongoing freshening in the fjord, indicating that the nutrient dynamics in the fjord were also influenced by inflows of fresher coastal waters. The observed trends of increasing silicate and decreasing nitrate concentrations are closely aligned with the freshening signal in Young Sound. Over the past two decades, surface waters have become at least one salinity unit fresher compared to the early 2000s, indicating a substantial increase in oceanic and glacial freshwater input (figures 3(b)–(e)).

4. Discussion

Arctic terrestrial runoff has long been known to contribute to the fjord and coastal nutrient supply [20, 37, 50], but understanding how Arctic greening may affect the terrestrially-derived load of dissolved nutrients, especially nitrogen, to fjords and coastal systems remains unclear. Previous studies have investigated nitrate cycling in the different compartments of the terrestrial-river-coastal continuum independently [21, 22, 26, 38, 56, 57]. However, a coherent understanding is hindered by a lack of interdisciplinary studies linking cross-ecosystem nitrate cycling with long-term field measurements. In addition to catchment-scale changes, shifts in the inflow of fresher coastal waters are starting to reshape nutrient dynamics in the region [32, 33]. Combined with terrestrial runoff to Arctic fjords, these changes alter the concentrations of dissolved nutrients, which play a key role in understanding

nutrient cycling within fjord ecosystems. While difficult to disentangle, the interplay between these different freshwater sources must be resolved to better assess and understand the broader nutrient dynamics, and subsequent impacts on productivity in Arctic coastal ecosystems.

4.1. Increased vegetation greening and reduced terrestrial nitrate input

The current greening of the tundra, indicated by a $\sim 12\%$ increase in annual mean NDVI_{max} , suggests an increase in tundra primary productivity (figure 2(b)). This increase in greening is comparable to the 10% greening observed across the broader Arctic region between 1982 and 2019 [2] and increased primary productivity leads to increased nutrient uptake, particularly nitrate, as tundra ecosystems are generally nitrogen-limited [39]. As a result, available nitrate is rapidly assimilated by terrestrial plants [17], reducing the amount that is exported into rivers and fjords [16, 58]. This trend is supported by a recent study in the Young Sound area showing a negative correlation between catchment greenness (NDVI) and riverine nitrate concentrations [56], indicating that terrestrial greening reduces dissolved nitrogen runoff to fjords. These reductions have also been observed in studies in other Arctic regions [37]. This overall decreasing trend in nitrate runoff from Zackenberg River to Young Sound is also supported by a recent analysis [57] documenting a substantial decrease in nitrate loads over 18 yrs, and that this decrease was not explained by reduced water runoff. Instead, the lower nitrate load was linked to decreasing snow stores, warming soils, and increased plant uptake in the catchment [57]. To account for year-to-year variability in data uncertainty, we conducted weighted linear regressions. These analyses confirmed the direction and significance of the trends observed in the unweighted regressions. The results are summarized in Supplementary table S1 and show that the overall conclusions remain robust across both approaches.

In the case of Young Sound, the reduction in nitrate concentrations in surface waters here hypothesized to in part be linked to terrestrial greening in the surrounding areas, as vegetation assimilates more of the available nitrate before it can reach the fjord. These findings contrast with previous research, which suggests that climate warming would lead to an increase in the export of inorganic nutrients in the Arctic [7, 28, 38, 58].

4.2. Changing nitrate input from coastal waters

In addition to changes in terrestrial inputs, we argue that changing nutrient dynamics in August in Young Sound are also shaped by shifts in the inflow of fresher coastal waters, contributing to the reduced salinity levels in the fjord [30, 31, 49]. Notably, Young Sound is now at least one salinity unit fresher compared to the early 2000s with a $\sim 2.5\%$ decrease in surface water salinity over the two decades (figures 1(e) and 3(b)–(e)), while seawater temperatures have remained relatively stable (data not shown). This freshening indicates a marked rise in freshwater inputs, driven by both an increase in local meltwater discharge and inflow of fresher coastal waters.

Recent studies suggest that increased transport of water masses from the Laptev Sea are now contributing to the freshening of coastal waters along the Northeast Greenland Shelf [32, 33]. They are characterized by low nitrate concentrations (average nitrate levels at 0–50 meters depth $< 1 \mu\text{M}$; [32]) and higher silicate levels (average silicate levels at 0–50 meters depth $> 6 \mu\text{M}$; [32]), a nutrient profile characteristic of the Laptev Sea and Northeast Greenland Shelf [32, 33, 38]. In addition, it is clear that biological drawdown of nitrate both locally in the fjord and upstream is important for the observed trends in August. A modelling study estimated that the average nitrate concentration on the Northeast Greenland Shelf in the upper 50 m at 80°N has decreased by $\sim 1 \text{ mmol m}^{-3}$ from 1970 to 2020 [59]. Combined with shelf wide increase in stratification [60] limiting vertical replenishment of nitrate and a general decrease in sea ice cover facilitating biological consumption which starts in May [61] it seems plausible that a combination of decreased upstream supply, earlier and/or increased biological consumption combined with decreased vertical replenishment could have contributed to a lower fjord supply of nitrate from coastal water exchange.

The influx of these nitrate-poor waters from the coastal ocean to the fjord has contributed to the observed decline in surface water nitrate concentrations in Young Sound, together with the effect of reduced terrestrial nitrate runoff. This is further supported by the finding that phosphate levels have remained stable, and silicate concentrations have increased by 115%, despite the significant decrease in nitrate in Young Sound. The marked rise in silicate levels may be linked to the increased glacial melt, as earlier studies indicate that the Greenland Ice Sheet plays a crucial role in enhancing the silicate pool in Greenland fjords and coastal waters [34, 62, 63]. In addition, contributions from snowmelt runoff flowing through terrestrial catchments via soil paths likely play a role, further elevating silicate concentrations in the fjord [64]. Local contributions, such as from the Zackenberg River, provide an average silicate concentration of $\sim 12.8 \mu\text{M}$ (T. Riis, unpubl. data), which also plays a substantive role in enhancing silicate concentrations in Young Sound. Combined, these sources, encompassing the meltwater runoff from the Greenland Ice Sheet, terrestrial runoff via soil flow pathways, and regional fluvial input, likely were responsible for the notable recent silicate enrichment. This multi-source input reflects the complex interplay of processes shaping nutrient dynamics within this fjord, highlighting the significant

biogeochemical influence of terrestrial and glacial interactions on coastal Arctic ecosystems. The combined impact of increased terrestrial greening, the inflow of fresher, nitrate-poor coastal waters, along with silicate-rich meltwater from the Greenland Ice Sheet, significantly alters nitrogen availability. The decreasing Chl *a* biomass despite an observed silicate enrichment and unchanged phosphate levels, emphasizes nitrogen as the key factor controlling the magnitude of fjord productivity.

5. Conclusions

This study hypothesizes that the observed reduction in summer nitrate inventories within the fjord has led to a decline in Chl *a* levels. The decrease in nitrate concentrations is likely driven by changes in nutrient supply from adjacent terrestrial and marine ecosystems, influenced by greening and freshening processes. While some proposed mechanisms remain to be fully quantified, the findings highlight the strong interconnectivity between ecosystems at various scales and suggest that climate-driven changes in terrestrial greening can alter coastal ecosystems along trajectories distinct from those observed in the open ocean. The interplay between terrestrial and oceanic drivers is complex and is likely to vary significantly across the Arctic. However, a concerted effort is required to better understand these processes to improve predictions of ecosystem changes and their implications for communities living along Arctic coastlines.

Acknowledgments

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17897/KQ4Z-SD22>; <https://doi.org/10.17897/DS37-V333>; <https://doi.org/10.17897/N626-SX63>; <https://doi.org/10.17897/GFWH-ZT42>; <https://doi.org/10.17897/CG48-0H12>; <https://doi.org/10.17897/K90N-8P82>; <https://doi.org/10.17897/1GTF-SX86>; <https://doi.org/10.22008/FK2/JMB3NQ>.

Funding

All data for this study were provided by the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (g-e-m.dk) which is funded by the Danish Environmental Protection Agency and the Danish Energy Agency. We gratefully acknowledge the contributions of the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF 185) to the Center for Ice-Free Arctic Research (CIFAR), Aarhus University. D.H.S received financial support from the Greenland Climate Research Centre (GCRC), Greenland Institute of Natural Resources and from the Arctic Research Centre of Aarhus University. S.R. received financial support from Aage V. Jensen Foundation and Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science. T.R. and J.L.T. have received funding from Carlsberg Foundation (#CF19-0131); L.C. L-H. has received funding from FACE-IT (The Future of Arctic Coastal Ecosystems-Identifying Transitions in Fjord Systems and Adjacent Coastal Areas) funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 869154. T.J-P. has received funding from GCRC and FACE-IT (EU Grant No. 869154). E.L.B., T.R.C., and M.M. have received funding from GreenFeedBack (Greenhouse gas fluxes and earth system feedbacks) funded by the European Union's HORIZON research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101056921. M.K.S. was funded by the HORIZON EUROPE project Polar Ocean Mitigation Project (grant agreement No 101136875).

Statement of authorship

Conceptualization: D H S, L C L-H, T R, J L T and E L B

Methodology: D H S, T R, S R, E L B, J L T

Investigation: M H S W, M K S, S R, E L B, T R C, J M H, N M S, M M and T J-P

Visualization: D H S, T R, S R E L B

Writing—original draft: D H S, T R, L C L-C

Writing—review & editing: All authors

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

ORCID iDs

Dorte H Sogaard <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6483-4747>
 Lars Chresten Lund–Hansen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5925-322X>
 Niels Martin Schmidt <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4166-6218>
 Søren Rysgaard <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1726-2958>
 Tenna Riis <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2501-4444>

References

- [1] Rantanen M, Karpechko A Y, Nordling K, Hyvärinen O, Ruosteenoja K, Vihma T and Laaksonen A 2022 The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979 *Commun. Earth. Environ.* **3** 168
- [2] Box J E *et al* 2021 Recent developments in Arctic climate observational indicators AMAP Arctic Climate Change update 2021: Key trends and impacts AMAP, 2021 7–20
- [3] Hernes P J, Tank S E, Sejr M K and Glud R N 2021 Element cycling and aquatic function in a changing Arctic *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **66** 1–16
- [4] Bring A, Fedorova I, Dibike Y, Hinzman L, Mård J, Mernild S H, Prowse T, Semenova O, Stuefer S L and Woo M K 2016 Arctic terrestrial hydrology: a synthesis of processes, regional effects, and research challenges *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosci.* **121** 621–49
- [5] Brown K A, Holding J M and Carmack E C 2020 Understanding regional and seasonal variability is key to gaining a Pan–Arctic perspective on Arctic Ocean freshening *Front. Mar. Sci.* **7** 606
- [6] Møller E F, Christensen A, Larsen J, Mankoff K D, Ribergaard M H, Sejr M, Wallhead P and Maar M 2023 The sensitivity of primary productivity in Disko Bay, a coastal Arctic ecosystem, to changes in freshwater discharge and sea ice cover *Ocean. Sci.* **19** 403–20
- [7] Santos-García M, Ganeshram R S, Tuerena R E, Debyser M, Husum K, Assmy P and Hop H 2022 Nitrate isotope investigations reveal future impacts of climate change on nitrogen inputs and cycling in Arctic fjords: Kongsfjorden and Rijpfjorden (Svalbard) *Biogeosciences* **19** 5973–6002
- [8] Arrigo K R and Dijken G L 2011 Secular trends in Arctic Ocean net primary production *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* **116** C09011
- [9] Lewis K M, Dijken G L and Arrigo K R 2020 Changes in phytoplankton concentration now drive increased Arctic Ocean primary production *Science* **369** 198–202
- [10] Box J E, Colgan W T, Christensen T R, Schmidt N M, Lund M, Parmentier F–J W, Brown R, Bhatt U S, Euskirchen E S and Romanovsky V E 2019 Key indicators of Arctic climate change: 1971–2017 *Environ. Res. Lett.* **14** 045010
- [11] Sejr M K, Poste A E and Renaud P E 2024 Multiple climatic drivers increase pace and consequences of ecosystem change in the Arctic Coastal Ocean *Limnology and Oceanography Letters* (<https://doi.org/10.1002/lol2.10431>)
- [12] Oziel L *et al* 2025 Climate change and terrigenous inputs decrease the efficiency of the future Arctic Ocean’s biological carbon pump *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **15** 171–9
- [13] Myers-Smith I H *et al* 2020 Complexity revealed in the greening of the Arctic *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **10** 106–17
- [14] Frost G V *et al* Tundra Greenness Arctic Report Card 2024, NOAA Technical Report OAR ARC; 24-09 <https://doi.org/10.25923/5t2g-fm41>
- [15] Miner R M, Turetsky M R, Malina E, Bartsch A, Tamminen J, MacGuire D A, Fix A, Sweeney C, Elder C D and Miller C E 2022 Permafrost carbon emissions in a changing Arctic *Nat. Rev. Earth. Environ.* **3** 55–67
- [16] Pedersen E P, Elberling B and Michelsen A 2022 Upslope release—downslope receipt? Multi-year plant uptake of permafrost–released nitrogen along an arctic hillslope *J. Ecol.* **110** 1896–912
- [17] Keuper F, van Bodegom P M, Dorrepaal E, Weedon J T, van Hal J, van Logtestijn R S P and Aerts R 2012 A frozen fest: thawing permafrost increases plant–available nitrogen in subarctic peatlands *Glob. Chang. Biol.* **18** 1998–2007
- [18] Ardyna M, Babin M, Gosselin M, Devred E, Rainville L and Tremblay J–E 2014 Recent Arctic Ocean sea ice loss triggers novel fall phytoplankton blooms *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **41** 6207–12
- [19] Ardyna M and Arrigo K R 2020 Phytoplankton dynamics in a changing Arctic Ocean *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **10** 892–903
- [20] Zhuang Y, Jin H, Cai W–J, Li H, Jin M, Qi D and Chen J 2021 Freshening leads to a three–decade trend of declining nutrients in the western Arctic Ocean *Environ. Res. Lett.* **16** 054047
- [21] Terhaar J, Lauerwald R, Regnier P, Gruber N and Bopp L 2021 Around one third of current Arctic Ocean primary production sustained by rivers and coastal erosion *Nat. Commun.* **12** 169
- [22] Gibson G A, Elliot S, Kinney J C, Piliouras A and Jeffery N 2022 Assessing the potential impact of river chemistry on Arctic coastal production *Front. Mar. Sci.* **9** 738363
- [23] Juul–Pedersen T, Arendt K, Mortensen J, Blicher M, Sogaard D H and Rygaard S 2015 , Seasonal and interannual phytoplankton production in a sub–Arctic tidewater outlet glacier fjord, SW Greenland *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* **52** 27–38
- [24] Meire L, Mortensen J, Meire P, Juul–Pedersen T, Sejr M K, Rysgaard S, Nygaard R, Huybrechts P and Meysman F J R 2017 Marine–terminating glaciers sustain high productivity in Greenland fjords *Glob. Chang. Biol.* **23** 5344–57
- [25] Hopwood M J *et al* 2020 Review article: how does glaciers discharge affect marine biogeochemistry and primary production in the Arctic? *Cryosphere* **14** 1347–83
- [26] Meire L, Paulsen M L, Meire P, Rysgaard S, Hopwood M J, Sejr M K, Stuart–Lee A, Sabbe K, Stock W and Mortensen J 2023 Glacier retreat alters downstream fjord ecosystem structure and function in Greenland *Nat. Geosci.* **16** 671–4
- [27] Sejr M K, Bruhn A, Dalsgaard T, Juul–Pedersen T, Stedmon C A, Blicher M, Meire L, Mankoff K D and Thyrring J 2022 Glacial meltwater determines the balance between autotrophic and heterotrophic processes in a Greenland fjord *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci.* **119** e2207024119
- [28] Vohnahme T, Nowak A, Hopwood M J, Meire L, Sogaard D H, Krawczyk D, Kalhagen K and Juul–Pedersen T 2023 Impact of winter freshwater from tidewater glaciers on fjords in Svalbard and Greenland; a review *Progr. Oceanogr.* **219** 103144

- [29] Singh R K, Vader A, Mundy C J, Søreide J E, Iken K, Dunton K H, de la Guardia L C, Sejr M K and Bêlanger S Satellite-derived photosynthetically available radiation at the coastal Arctic seafloor *Remote Sens.* **14** 5180
- [30] de Steur L, Petalta-Ferriz C and Pavlova O 2018 Freshwater export in the East Greenland Current freshens the North Atlantic *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **45** 13359–66
- [31] Boone W, Rysgaard S, Carlson D F, Meire L, Kirillov S, Mortensen J, Dmitrenko I, Vergeynst L and Sejr M K 2018 Coastal freshening prevents fjord bottom water renewal in Northeast Greenland: a mooring study from 2003 to 2015 *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **45** 2726–33
- [32] Willcox E W *et al* 2023 An updated view of the water masses on the Northeast Greenland shelf and their link to the Laptev Sea and Lena River *J. Geophys. Res. Ocean* **128** e2022JC019052
- [33] Rysgaard S, Mortensen J, Haxen M, Gillard L C and Risgaard-Pedersen N 2024 Summer hydrography conditions at proglacial fjord entrances along East Greenland *J. Geophys. Res. Lett. Ocean*. **129** e2023JC020665
- [34] Meire L, Meire P, Struyf E, Krawczyk D W, Arendt K E, Yde J C, Juul-Pedersen T, Hopwood M J, Rysgaard S and Meysman F J R 2016 High export of dissolved silica from the Greenland Ice Sheet *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **43** 9173–82
- [35] Sun X *et al* 2018 Stable silicon isotopic compositions of the Lena River and its tributaries: Implications for silicon delivery to the Arctic Ocean *Geoch. Cosmochim. Acta.* **241** 120–33
- [36] Hatton J E, Ng H C, Meire L, Woodward E M S, Leng M J, Coath C D, Stuart-Lee A, Wang T, Annett A L and Hendry K R 2023 Silicon isotopes highlight the role of glaciated fjords in modifying coastal waters *J. Geophys Res: Biogeosciences* **128** e2022JG007242
- [37] Tank S E *et al* 2023 Recent trends in the chemistry of major northern rivers signal widespread Arctic change *Nat. Geosci.* **16** 789–96
- [38] Thibodeau B, Bauch D and Voss M 2017 Nitrogen dynamic in Eurasian coastal Arctic ecosystem: insight from nitrogen isotope *G. Biogeochem. Cycl.* **31** 836–49
- [39] Coch C, Juhls B, Lamoureux S F, Lafrenière M J, Fritz M, Heim B and Lantuit H 2019 Comparisons of dissolved organic matter and its optical characteristics in small low and high Arctic catchments *Biogeosciences* **16** 4535–53
- [40] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring MarineBasis Zackenberg - Water column - Water Phosphate Concentration (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.17897/KQ4Z-SD22>)
- [41] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring MarineBasis Zackenberg - Water column - Pigment concentration (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.17897/DS 37-V333>)
- [42] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring MarineBasis Zackenberg - Water column - Water Nitrate+Nitrite Concentration (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.17897/N626-SX63>)
- [43] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring MarineBasis Zackenberg - Water column - Water Silicate Concentration (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.17897/GFWH-ZT42>)
- [44] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring MarineBasis Zackenberg - Water column - CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0] (2024). Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (<https://doi.org/10.17897/CG 48-0H12>)
- [45] Sogaard D H, Sorrell B K, Sejr M K, Andersen P, Rysgaard S, Hansen P J, Skyttå A, Lemcke S and Lund-Hansen L C 2021 An under-ice bloom of mixotrophic haptophytes in low nutrient and freshwater-influenced Arctic waters *Sci Rep.* **11** 2915
- [46] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring BioBasis Zackenberg - Vegetation - Plot NDVI (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.17897/K90N-8P82>)
- [47] Schmidt N M, Hansen L M and Hansen J BioBasis - conceptual design and sampling procedures of the biological programme of Zackenberg Basic, 24th edition ed. Department of Bioscience, University of Aarhus, Denmark, Roskilde (2021) (https://g-e-m.dk/fileadmin/g-e-m/GEM/BioBasisManual_2019.pdf)
- [48] Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring GeoBasis Zackenberg - Hydrology - River_water_chemistry (Version 1.0). [Data set] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.17897/1GTF-SX86>)
- [49] Sejr M K, Stedmon C A, Bendtsen J, Abermann J, Juul-Pedersen T, Mortensen J and Rysgaard S 2017 Evidence of local and regional freshening of Northeast Greenland coastal waters *Sci Rep.* **7** 13183
- [50] Rysgaard S and Glud R (ed) 2007 Carbon cycling in Arctic marine ecosystems: case study Young Sound *Meddelelser om Grønland* (Bioscience) **58** 13–23
- [51] Simpson J, Brown J, Matthews J and Allen G 1990 Tidal straining, density currents, and stirring in the control of estuarine stratification *Estuaries* **13** 125–32
- [52] Jones E P, Anderson L G and Swift J H 1998 Distribution of Atlantic and Pacific waters in the upper Arctic Ocean: implications for circulation *J. Geophys. Res. Lett.* **25** 765–8
- [53] Randelhoff A, Holding J, Janout M, Sejr M K, Babin M, Tremblay J-E and Alkire M B 2020 Pan-Arctic ocean primary production constrained by turbulent nitrate fluxes *Front. Mar. Sci.* **7** 150
- [54] Bendtsen J, Rysgaard S, Carlson D F, Meire L and Sejr M K 2021 Vertical mixing in stratified fjords near tidewater outlet glaciers along Northwest Greenland *J. Geophys. Res. Ocean.* **126** e2020JC016898
- [55] Box J E Daily CARRA data at Zackenberg 1991 to 2021, GEUS Dataverse, V1 daily 2m air temperature (t2m) (2022). <https://doi.org/10.22008/FK2/JMB3NQ>
- [56] Riis T, Tank J L, Holmboe C M H, Giménez-Grau P, Mastepanov M, Catalàn N, Stott D, Hansen B, Kristensen S M and Pastor A 2023 Links between stream water nitrogen and terrestrial vegetation in Northeast Greenland. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* **128** e2023JG007688
- [57] Speir S L, Tank J L, Pastor A, Muller M F, Mastepanov M and Riis T 2024 Catchment-scale thawing and greening decreases long-term nitrogen export in NE Greenland *Environ. Res. Lett.* **19** 054031
- [58] McGovern M, Pavlov A K, Deininger A, Granskog M A, Leu E, Søreide J E and Poste A E 2020 Terrestrial inputs drive seasonality in organic matter and nutrient biogeochemistry in a high Arctic fjord system *Front. Mar. Sci.* **7** 542563
- [59] Tuerena R E *et al* 2021 An Arctic strait of two halves: the changing dynamics of nutrient uptake and limitation across the Fram Strait *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycl.* **35** e2021GB006961
- [60] Gjelstrup C V B, Sejr M K, de Steur L, Christiansen J S, Granskog M A, Koch B P, Møller E F, Winding M H S and Stedmon C A 2022 Vertical redistribution of principle water masses on the Northeast Greenland Shelf *Nat. Commun.* **13** 7660
- [61] Vernet M, Ellingsen I, Marchese C, Bêlanger S, Cape M, Slagstad D and Matrai P A 2021 Spatial variability in rates of net primary production (NPP) and onset of the spring bloom in Greenland Shelf waters *Progr. Oceanograph.* **198** 102655
- [62] Hawkings J, Wadham J L, Benning L G, Hendry K R, Tranter M, Tedstone A, Nienow P and Raiswell R 2017 Ice sheets as a missing source of silica to the polar oceans *Nat. Commun.* **8** 14198
- [63] Oksman M *et al* 2022 Impact of freshwater runoff from the Southwest Greenland Ice Sheet on fjord productivity since the late 19th century *T. C.* **16** 2471–91
- [64] Blaen P J, Hannah D M, Brown L E and Milner A M 2014 Water source dynamics of high Arctic river basins *Hydro. Proc.* **28** 3521–38